

COMPREHENSIVE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC ENDOMETRITIS

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Severity: The chronicity of the disease occurs due to timely treatment of the acute stage of the disease or premature completion of therapy. The penetration of pathogenic microflora into the uterine cavity occurs through the vagina. Triggering factors for the development of inflammation: Childbirth, abortion, gynecological operations; Diagnostic manipulations; Menstruation, intercourse during menstruation; Infectious processes developing in other organs;

The inflammatory process occurs with periodic exacerbations and remissions. But even during the clinical course, there are menstrual disorders, pain in the lower abdomen and mucous discharge. During the chronic process, changes in the structure of the endometrium occur. The functionality of the inner uterine layer can be restored only with systemic therapy.

The purpose and objectives of the research. In the chronic stage of the disease, the symptoms are smooth, so it becomes difficult to diagnose. But the gynecologist's experience, modern equipment technologies and laboratory tests allow to make an accurate diagnosis.

Research materials and methods. The use of information diagnostic methods includes general and biochemical blood tests, general urinalysis, pelvic ultrasound, diagnostic curettage for bacteriological and pathomorphological examination. A smear and secretion analysis is carried out, the purpose of which is to determine the type of pathogen.

If the diagnosis is suspected, computer tomography, MRI, hysteroscopy are used and medical advice is prescribed. After the diagnosis, a complex treatment scheme is prescribed.

Research results: The goal of treatment is to restore endometrial tissue and a woman's ability to conceive. Antibiotics are needed to eliminate the infectious process caused by the introduction of bacterial pathogens. Products with a wide range of effects are used. Complex therapy of the disease includes the use of anti-inflammatory, antifungal agents and antispasmodics aimed at eliminating symptoms.

Conclusions: The disease should be treated for a long time, for example, hormone treatment with progesterone preparations lasts 6-12 months. Even if the disease disappears after menopause. In recent years, the use of the intrauterine spiral Mirena in the treatment of endometriosis has gained popularity, which determines the popular synthetic analogue of progesterone every day. It will work for 5 years and if necessary, it will be replaced after this

period. Endometriosis cannot be cured forever, but with the help of this spiral, the disease can be reversed.

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